

OXYGEN SATURATION PROFILE OF PARTICIPANTS SCHOOL PARALYMPICS GAMES 2017

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Abstract

Pulse oximetry is one of the most common forms of monitoring in the critical care setting. Through a finger oximeter, it is possible to verify the presence of hypoxemia. The objective of this study was to verify the Heart Rate (HR) and the peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂) in athletes participating School Paralympics Games no year the 2017. Participated in the study 49 male athletes of the CP Football and Boccia Sports. The physiological variables heart rate (HR) and the hemoglobin oxygen saturation (SpO₂) were measured at rest. the results demonstrated average of SpO₂ of Soccer Football PC modality for 94.73 ± 7.2 and FC 84.3 ± 14.8 . On the other hand, athletes of the Paralympic Bocce had the mean SpO₂ value of 82.15 ± 22.0 and HR with 81.25 ± 29.6 . Individuals with less fitness undergo oxygen desaturation in vigorous exercise. Concluding that oxygen desaturation is related as the maximum volume of oxygen value and the physical level of the athletes. Because it is a pioneering study in the area of Paralympic sport with athletes who present impairments (Cerebral Palsy and others), we realize the need for a special attention in their level of blood saturation, since the lack of oxygen in the blood can have relations to a training of high intensity that will lead to hyperventilation done wrong or inadequate.

Keywords Disability, Oxygen Saturation of Hemoglobin, Heart rate, Cerebral Palsy.

Introduction

Cerebral palsy (CP) is a sequela due to a brain injury or aggression, and may have different characteristics depending on the location and extent of the lesion. According to Koman et al. (2004), the term PC describes a sequela of non-progressive character that affects the Central Nervous System (CNS) causing postural deficits, tonics and the execution of movements. The diagnosis is clinical, and an injury is reported during the developmental phase of the CNS from conception to two years of age.

Among the modalities practiced by people with CP and presenting other associated impairments, such as stroke or cranio-encephalic trauma, are PC soccer and bocce. PC Football follows the rules of FIFA with some modifications, of which stand out: the lateral throw can be done by rolling the ball; non-existence of the impediment rule; the team consists of seven players, including the goalkeeper; the field has maximum dimensions of 75 meters in length by 55 meters in width; and the match is played in two 30-minute periods (IFCPF, 2018a).

As in other adapted sports, PC Football presents a functional classification system, taking into account its deficiency and functionality, assigning to the players functional classes: FT1, FT2 and FT3 (IFCPF, 2018b).

People with PC who present severe motor impairment also have the possibility of practicing Bocce, a modality that has the purpose of bringing the largest number of colored balls to the white. The boules can be played individually, in pairs or in teams, being a mixed sport that men and women compete together and equally. In addition to PC athletes, people with other disabilities may also participate, as long as they have the required degree of disability and proven. The functional classification for the practice is according to the degree of motor impairment, and the deficiency of the athlete, being: BC1, BC2, BC4, BC3 (ANDE, 2018).

Both Football and other collective modalities that require more intensive training, demonstrate the need to monitor and evaluate aspects related to physiological issues, among them, O₂ saturation. In this sense, sports training requires physiological and metabolic responses that cause cardiorespiratory adjustments, such as increased heart rate (HR), respiratory rate, blood pressure, in order to maintain blood perfusion adequate to the demand of oxygen demanded by the muscles during physical exertion (WHITE et al., 2016). This monitoring has as main purpose the early detection of hypoxemia in several situations and the monitoring of perfusion and circulation (HINKELBEIN et al., 2007). Therefore, pulse oximetry is a noninvasive method of measuring oxygen saturation of hemoglobin (SpO₂) and heart rate (HR), the high utilization of the method is justified due to practicality, reliability, ease of handling, low cost and mainly, to present a response in a short period of time. The objective of this study was to verify the Heart Rate (HR) and Oxygen Saturation of Hemoglobin (SpO₂) in athletes participating in the School Paralympics Games of 2017

Methods

The sample consisted of 49 male athletes, 30 athletes from PC Football and 19 from Paralympic Bocce participating in the School Paralympics Games of the year 2017

With respect to ethical aspects, this study was submitted and approved by the Ethics Committee of the State University of Campinas - UNICAMP, CAAE: 80601917.7.0000.5404, N^o of opinion 2,475,044. The athletes were informed about the research objectives and the procedures to which they would be submitted and requested the signing of the Informed Consent Form (TCLE) for the study participation.

The physiological variables of peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂) and heart rate (HR) were measured at rest using the Realdox pulse model oximeter model MD300C4. The equipment calculates the amount of oxygen carried by the blood and its measurement is based on the difference between levels of hemoglobin (red blood cells). This occurs because oxygenated and

non-oxygenated hemoglobin are of different colors, and when the two beams of infrared light (an invisible and a red light) emitted by the device penetrate the skin of the finger, which is thin and translucent, differentiate absorption of these lights and identifies the concentration of each of them, giving the result by means of the saturation percentage of the oxygen. Data was tabulated through the Microsoft Excel 2007® package.

Results

The values average schoolchildren found for SpO₂ of the Football Soccer modality were 94.73 ± 7.2 and the FC 84.3 ± 14.8. On the other hand, the athletes of the Paralympic Bocce had Average SpO₂ values of 82.15 ± 22.0 and HR with 81.25 ± 29.6.

Table 1: Average results of SpO₂ and FC of the modalities evaluated.

Modality	N° Athletes	SpO ₂	FC
PC Football	30	94,73±7,2	84,3±14,8
Bocce	19	82,15±22,0	81,25±29,6

Conclusion and discussion

Individuals with less fitness undergo oxygen desaturation in vigorous exercise. Concluding that oxygen desaturation is related as the maximum VO₂ value and the physical level of the athletes (MIYACHI, 1999). Because it is a pioneering study in the area of Paralympic sport with athletes who such present deficiencies, we realize the need for a special attention in their level of blood saturation, since the lack of oxygen in the blood can have relations to a training of high intensity that will lead to hyperventilation done wrong or inadequate

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Oxygen Saturation Profile of participants School Paralympics

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